

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
1

SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, SCIENTIFIC AND
TECHNICAL ACADEMIC JOURNAL

**TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS**

Scopus II

Journal integrated into
the Scopus database

Acceptance of articles

PUBLISHED EVERY MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS

**PROFESSORS-TEACHERS, SPECIALISTS
AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHERS.**

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 90 955 49 28

https://t.me/econoscitech_2100

NOVEMBER, 2024

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

**Zufarova Nozima
Gulamiddinovna**

DSc., Dean of Tourism
Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

**Makhmudov Nosir
Makhmudovich**

DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

**Shomurodov Ravshan
Tursunkulovich**

PhD, Associate professor

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-
INTEGRATION" HAS BEEN
REGISTERED UNDER THE
NUMBER C-5669651 BY
THE AGENCY FOR
INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone:

93-718-40-07

Website:

econoscitech-integration-
journal.uz

Email:

sq143235@gmail.com

Electronic publication, Issue 1. 186 pages.
Approved for publication on October 1, 2024.

Editorial

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education,
Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich, DSc, Prof. Rector of Tashkent State University of
Economics

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for
Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional
educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Musaeva Shoira Azimovna, professor at Samarkand State Institute of Economics
and Service

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ochilova Xilola Farmonovna, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Abidova Dilfuza Igamberdiyevna, PhD, Prof., of TSUE

Tokunaga Masahiro, professor, PhD of
Economics of the Faculty of Business
and Commerce, Kansai University,
Osaka, Japan tokunaga@kansai-u.ac.jp

Debasis Das, professor Department of
Computer Science, Webster University
in Tashkent, PhD, MCA, MBA, MSc
(Computer Science)

Nitin Goje, professor and Program Lead
- Computer Science, Webster University
in Tashkent, PhD, MCA, MBA, MSc
(Computer Science)

Editor-in-Chief's Desk

Dear Esteemed Professors and Researchers,

We often hear about your aspirations to publish articles in international journals. Inspired by your academic potential, we are pleased to announce the launch of Econoscitech-Integration, an international scientific journal specializing in socio-economics, science and technology, and innovation. Our journal is committed to fostering collaborative ties with prominent research centers across Central Asia and Europe, promoting the exchange of new knowledge and innovations.

Through Econoscitech-Integration, we aim to bring valuable research, analyses, and practical insights focused on the socio-economic development of our country to a wide audience. Here, we provide an opportunity to address issues in economics, technology, innovation, and social sciences through modern scientific approaches and to implement them in practice. The research published in our journal covers not only theoretical knowledge but also addresses relevant and impactful practical topics.

If you have innovative ideas in fields such as economics, engineering, education, tourism, or other critical areas, and wish to explore solutions, we invite you to collaborate with us. We value every article submitted, recognizing its importance for societal and national development, and we approach each submission with dedicated attention.

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

CONTENTS

Editor-in-Chief's Desk.....	3
Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	
Monetary policy: theoretical and practical issues.....	5
Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich	
Analysis of developed countries in the study of the country's investment attractiveness.....	17
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli	
Calculate equivalent units, allocate to another process (finished goods), and evaluate work in process.....	27
Avilkasimov Shakhzodbek	
Food security problems.....	33
Shukurov Tohirjon Izzatullo ugli	
Waste management in the dairy industry.....	37
Shukurov Izzatullo Khikmatullaevich	
Пути развития фондового рынка на основе цифровых технологий.....	45
Шукурова Луиза Баратовна, Эшдавлатов Боймурод Соатович	

WASTE MANAGEMENT IN THE DAIRY INDUSTRY

Shukurov Izzatullo Khikmatullaevich

*Candidate of technical sciences, associate professor, head
of the department of "Service" of the Samarkand Institute of
Economics and Service (140100, Samarkand, Amir Temur St.,*

Email: shukurovi342@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5916-8964>

Abstract: The study examines the process of thermoacid coagulation of milk proteins, ensuring low-waste production and environmental protection by maximizing the extraction of whey proteins in combination with casein. Scientifically substantiated modes of preliminary thermal treatment and coagulation of proteins in heat-treated milk have been established, ensuring the highest degree of utilization of raw material solids and playing a significant role in expanding the range of protein products.

Key words: waste-free technology, whey, thermoacid coagulation, whey proteins, degree of dry matter utilization.

Аннотация: В исследовании рассматривается процесс термокислотной коагуляции молочных белков, обеспечивающий безотходное производство и защиту окружающей среды за счет максимального извлечения сывороточных белков в сочетании с казеином. Установлены научно обоснованные режимы предварительной термической обработки и коагуляции белков в термически обработанном молоке, обеспечивающие наивысшую степень использования сухих веществ сырья и играющие значительную роль в расширении ассортимента белковых продуктов.

Ключевые слова: безотходная технология, сыворотка, термокислотная коагуляция, сывороточные белки, степень использования сухих веществ.

Annotatsiya: Tadqiqotda sut oqsillarining termo-kislotali koagulyatsiya jarayoni o'rganilib, bu jarayon chiqindisiz ishlab chiqarishni ta'minlash va atrof-muhitni himoya qilishga qaratilgan. Ushbu jarayon orqali zardob oqsillari va kazeinni maksimal darajada ajratib olish imkoniyati yaratiladi. Oldindan termik ishlov berilgan sutdagi oqsillarning koagulyatsiya qilish uchun ilmiy asoslangan rejimlari ishlab chiqildi, bu esa xomashyo quruq moddasining yuqori darajada o'zlashtirilishini va oqsil mahsulotlarining assortimentini kengaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Tayanch iboralar: chiqindisiz texnologiya, zardob, termo-kislotali koagulyatsiya, zardob oqsillari, quruq modda o'zlashtirish darajasi.

1. INTRODUCTION

As modern production develops with increasing scale and growth rates, the need for developing and implementing low- and zero-waste technologies becomes increasingly relevant. "Waste-free technology is a production method in which all raw materials and energy are used most rationally and comprehensively in the cycle: raw material resources - production - consumption -

secondary resources, and any impact on the environment does not disrupt its normal functioning." Creating waste-free production is a very complex and lengthy process, with the intermediate stage being low-waste production. Low-waste production refers to processes where environmental impact levels do not exceed those allowed by sanitary and hygienic standards (i.e., Maximum Permissible Concentrations, MPC). At the same time, for technical, economic, organizational, or other reasons, a portion of raw materials and materials may still become waste and require long-term storage or disposal [1, 2].

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the "UN Declaration on Low-Waste and Zero-Waste Technology and the Use of Waste", adopted in Geneva in 1979, waste-free technology is defined as a principle for the functioning of industries and agriculture, ensuring rational use of all raw material and energy components while maintaining ecological balance. This principle of zero waste received international legal status and was required to be adopted into the legislation of individual states [3].

The industrial processing of milk based on waste-free technology principles—complete extraction of all components, rational use of intermediate and by-products, reduction of regulatory losses, and elimination of unused waste—is among the most important reserves for increasing the volume of dairy products and enhancing production efficiency. Waste-free technology eliminates environmental pollution and has significant ecological importance [4].

Implementing the principles of waste-free technology in the dairy industry is possible through the integrated use of all milk components for food production or through the separate extraction of components with subsequent processing of low-fat milk raw materials and intermediate products [4, 5]. Since whey, a valuable biological raw material, is often discarded as production waste, polluting the environment, it would be prudent to utilize it as a primary raw material for preparing food products [6].

The issue of effectively utilizing whey exists in all countries with highly developed dairy industries. In countries like France, the USA, Sweden, and Canada, the dairy industry processes 50–95% of dairy waste [7]. Whey processing today is a relevant solution that reduces environmental pollution and elevates the efficiency of dairy enterprises through waste-free production [8].

According to environmental safety considerations, 1 ton of whey discharged into the sewer pollutes water bodies to the same extent as 100 m³ of household waste. Greening dairy production has become an essential part of the sustainable development concepts for enterprises in recent years. This includes environmentally oriented technical and technological advancements in the dairy industry, although a clear and comprehensive awareness of the need for green production is still lacking [6].

The animal proteins in whey, when released into the environment, cause persistent organic pollution. Discharging whey (or whey-containing water) into soil inhibits plant development, and with prolonged exposure, renders the soil practically infertile. The high acidity of whey leads to soil acidification and the destruction of its normal microflora. When whey enters water or soil, its organic substances oxidize, producing large amounts of toxic compounds. These environmental impacts necessitate a more rigorous approach to processing secondary raw materials from the dairy industry [9].

Whey is a highly valuable secondary raw material, containing nearly all biologically active substances present in milk. However, it should not be regarded as merely a by-product due to its rich content of beneficial microelements and vitamins. Whey includes components such as lactoferrin, immunoglobulins, a full set of B vitamins, vitamin C, nicotinic acid, choline, vitamin A, vitamin E, biotin, and minerals such as calcium (Ca), potassium (K), phosphorus (P), iron (Fe), and zinc (Zn), along with all essential amino acids [10].

Existing whey disposal technologies, such as discharge into sewers or filtration fields, lead to severe environmental consequences. These include disruptions in sewage treatment plants, mineral salinization of soil, and groundwater contamination. Therefore, deep processing of whey

and reducing its wastage is critical not only for economic reasons but also for environmental protection [11].

To ensure comprehensive processing of dairy raw materials and increase the volume of whey processing, it is advisable to attract investments for modernization and the creation of additional specialized facilities for whey processing. Modern whey processing technologies include drying, thickening, ultrafiltration, production of protein concentrates, production of milk sugar and its derivative lactulose, as well as applications in the food industry, feed production, and the production of ethyl alcohol [12].

In terms of creating low-waste production, increasing product yield and enhancing its nutritional and biological value through the maximal use of all protein components of raw materials, high-temperature coagulation of milk proteins is particularly promising. The highest degree of fat and protein utilization is achieved through high-temperature coagulation of milk proteins using acids and calcium chloride, referred to as thermoacid and thermocalcium coagulation, respectively. If the efficiency of acid coagulation (without heating) is set at 100%, the relative degrees of protein utilization during rennet, thermoacid, and thermocalcium coagulation are 94%, 114%, and 116%, respectively [13].

Based on the literature review, this research aims to study the process of thermal acid coagulation of milk proteins, focusing on maximizing the extraction of whey proteins in combination with casein, thereby ensuring low-waste production and environmental protection.

3. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY.

The following research methods were employed: Titratable acidity: Measured according to GOST 3624-67. Active acidity: Determined using the pH 222 device.

Mass fraction of fat: Measured according to GOST 5867-69. Mass fraction of moisture and dry matter: Determined according to GOST 3626-73. Content of nitrogenous compounds: Measured using the VNIIMS method. Each analysis was repeated five times to ensure accuracy. It is well-established that heating milk denatures whey proteins, which then precipitate with casein under acidic conditions. In such conditions, where the stability of colloidal milk systems decreases, the sediment properties and precipitation completeness depend on several parameters. The key factors include:

- The temperature regime of the coagulation process.
- The ratio of coagulant to milk, which influences the charge of colloidal particles and their aggregative stability.
- The type and temperature of the coagulant, which play a significant role.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In preliminary experiments, whey with an acidity of 130–140 °T, prepared by adding pure cultures of lactic acid bacteria at 5%, was used as a coagulant. The coagulation temperature was adjusted to 35–40 °C prior to use.

To determine the optimal heating temperature ranges and analyze the effects of different temperatures on physicochemical and organoleptic properties and the degree of solids utilization, skim milk was heated to the following temperatures: 80, 85, 90, and 95 °C.

At these temperatures, pre-prepared acid whey was added in small portions in a thin stream along the wall of the vessel, while being carefully mixed. The whey volume constituted 10% of the milk volume. The mixture was left undisturbed for 5 minutes. The isolated proteins were filtered through Mylar cloth and then subjected to self-pressing for 1–2 hours. The total volume of the skim milk and whey mixture was 1.5 liters. The results of studies of the obtained protein masses and the released whey are given in Table 1.

Table1

The influence of different heating temperatures on physicochemical, organoleptic characteristics and the degree of utilization of milk solids

Coagulation temperature, °C	Protein mass				Whey	
	Degree of use of dry substances, %	pH	Taste and smell	Consistency	Mass fraction of protein, %	Mass fraction of dry substances, %
80	22,9	6,00± 0,01	Clean with a slight pasteurization taste	Rough, crumbly	0,520± 0,003	7,00± 0,035
85	39,7	6,01± 0,01	Clean with a slight pasteurization taste	Rough, crumbly	0,443± 0,003	6,55± 0,030
90	43,1	6,00± 0,01	Clean with a taste of pasteurization	Dense, grainy	0,397± 0,004	6,35± 0,037
95	44,7	6,03± 0,01	Clean with a taste of pasteurization	Hard, rubbery	0,359± 0,005	6,18± 0,030

The study of the effect of heat exposure duration on the utilization degree of dry substances in protein masses was conducted at a milk heating temperature of 95°C and an optimal whey addition dose of 10% of the milk volume. Different durations at 95°C were investigated: 10–15 seconds, 5 minutes, 10 minutes, and 20 minutes. The volume of the mixture and the conditions for thermal acid coagulation were the same as in previous experiments, except that, in addition to skim milk, normalized milk with a fat content of 1.1% was also used as the starting raw material. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

To study the effect of coagulation temperature on the properties and quality of the resulting protein masses, the starting raw materials (skimmed and normalized milk with a fat content of no more than 1.1%) were subjected to thermal treatment under previously established conditions (95°C with a holding time of 5 minutes) and coagulated with acid whey at temperatures of 95, 85, 75, and 65°C for 5 minutes. After separating the whey and self-pressing for 60 minutes, the resulting protein mass and the released whey were subjected to analysis.

The study of changes in the physicochemical properties of skim and fat protein masses was conducted by obtaining them at the coagulation temperature of proteins in heat-treated milk at 65, 75, 85, and 95°C (Table 3).

Analyzing the data obtained at all four studied temperature values, it can be observed that the heating temperature has a significant effect on the degree of utilization of dry substances.

Table 2
The influence of the duration of heat exposure on the degree of utilization of dry substances of protein masses

No.	Heating temperature, °C	Duration of heat exposure, min	Degree of utilization of dry substances, %		Mass fraction of protein in the released whey, %
			Low-fat mass	protein mass	
1	95	0,16-0,25	45,8	45,6	0,364± 0,004
2	95	5	46,1	47,5	0,360± 0,053
3	95	10	46,6	48,3	0,352± 0,003

4	95	20	47,0	48,6	0,350± 0,008
---	----	----	------	------	--------------

As shown in Table 1, as the heating temperature decreases from 95°C to 80°C, the degree of utilization of dry substances decreases from 44.7% to 22.9%. When the heating temperature increases to 95°C, the mass fraction of proteins and dry substances in the released whey decreases by 30.95% and 11.72%, respectively, compared to heating at 80°C.

The increase in the degree of utilization of dry substances in protein masses with higher heating temperatures is associated with the denaturation and joint release of whey proteins and casein. Whey proteins are particularly sensitive to heat, making their degree of denaturation highly dependent on the heating temperature.

However, within the studied heating temperature range, there is no significant effect on the active acidity of the protein masses, and their organoleptic characteristics change only slightly. As the heating temperature decreases, the consistency of the protein masses transitions from solid and rubbery to grainy and crumbly.

As stated above, the degree of utilization of protein solids is closely related to the denaturation of whey proteins. Since the denaturation of whey proteins depends not only on the heating temperature but also on the duration of heat exposure, this factor was also studied.

As shown in the research results (Table 2), increasing the duration of heat exposure results in a noticeable increase in the mass fraction of dry substances in protein masses and a decrease in the content of soluble whey proteins in the released whey due to further denaturation. Specifically, increasing the thermal exposure duration from 10–15 seconds to 5 and 20 minutes raises the degree of utilization of dry substances in skim and fatty protein masses by 0.3% and 1.2%, and by 1.9% and 3.0%, respectively. Concurrently, the mass fraction of whey proteins in the whey decreases by 0.36% and 2.6%, respectively.

However, despite the slight improvement in the degree of utilization of dry substances, prolonged thermal exposure significantly alters the physicochemical properties of milk and entails considerable energy costs. Therefore, in subsequent experiments, the duration of thermal exposure was limited to 5 minutes.

The study of the duration of exposure of the mixture at the coagulation temperature after adding acid whey showed that this factor significantly affects the mass of dry substances in protein masses. Holding the mixture for 5 minutes increases the mass of dry substances in protein masses by 20%. However, further increasing the holding time has virtually no effect on the mass of dry substances in protein masses.

Table 3

Physico-chemical properties of protein masses and whey

Milk temperature before coagulation, °C	Dose acid whey, %	Mixture temperature, °C	Protein mass				Whey		
			Degree of use of dry substances, %	Mass moisture content, %	pH	Titra-ble acidity, °T	Mass fraction of protein, %	Titra-ble acidity, °T	pH
Low-fat protein mass									
65	17,3	55	45,4	73,71± 0,21	5,78± 0,01	140,0±1,8	0,362± 0,004	26,9± 0,4	5,73± 0,01
75	15,3	65	46,1	72,42± 0,37	5,92± 0,01	127,0±1,7	0,358± 0,005	22,6± 0,3	5,85± 0,01

85	12,5	75	46,0	71,83± 0,39	6,03± 0,01	113,0±1, 5	0,360± 0,019	20,1± 0,3	5,89± 0,01
95	10	89	46,1	70,79± 0,26	6,03± 0,01	99,0±1,7	0,360± 0,050	19,0± 0,4	5,90± 0,01
Fatty protein mass									
65	18,1	55	46,3	69,80± 0,42	5,80± 0,01	137,0±1, 8	0,359± 0,052	25,0± 0,4	5,76± 0,01
75	15,5	65	47,5	68,47± 0,16	5,95± 0,01	125,0±1, 7	0,360± 0,005	22,2± 0,3	5,85± 0,02
85	12,7	75	47,1	67,73± 0,26	6,04± 0,01	110,0±1, 6	0,360± 0,060	20,0± 0,4	5,90± 0,01
95	10	89	47,5	66,76± 0,16	6,12± 0,01	96,0±1,6	0,339± 0,012	19,0± 0,4	5,91± 0,01

Thus, the degree of utilization of dry substances, the mass fraction of moisture, active acidity, and organoleptic properties of protein masses obtained by thermal acid coagulation of milk proteins are influenced by the heating temperature, the duration of thermal exposure, the active acidity of the lactic acid, and the duration of exposure of the mixture at the coagulation temperature.

It is important to highlight the significant role of milk protein coagulation temperatures in determining the consistency of the resulting protein masses. It was observed that as the coagulation temperature decreases from 95°C to 80°C, the consistency of the protein masses improves noticeably, transitioning from a hard, rubbery texture to a grainy, crumbly texture similar to cottage cheese. However, this improvement in consistency is accompanied by a substantial reduction in the degree of utilization of dry substances in the protein masses.

Therefore, the most suitable thermal acid coagulation mode, which ensures the highest degree of utilization of milk solids, is as follows: Heating temperature: 95°C with a holding time of 5 minutes. Whey addition: 10% whey with an acidity of 135–140°T, at a temperature of 35–40°C. Holding time: The mixture is held at the coagulation temperature for 5 minutes.

As indicated by the research results (Table 3), the coagulation temperature of milk proteins significantly affects the physicochemical properties of the resulting protein masses. It was established that as the coagulation temperature decreases, the required dose of added acid whey increases. For example, at a coagulation temperature of 95°C, the amount of added acid whey is 10%, whereas at 65°C, this increases to 17.8–18.1%.

Increasing the dose of added acidic whey as the coagulation temperature of milk proteins decreases noticeably reduces the active acidity and increases the titratable acidity of the protein masses. This has a positive effect on the organoleptic characteristics of the resulting protein masses, imparting a pleasant milky taste and aroma.

It has been established that, due to the preliminary heat treatment of milk at high temperatures, a further decrease in the coagulation temperature of milk proteins does not significantly affect the degree of utilization of dry substances in protein masses. The data presented in the table indicate that when the coagulation temperature of milk proteins decreases from 95°C to 65°C, the degree of utilization of dry substances in fat-free and fatty protein masses remains at the same level as at a coagulation temperature of 95°C. This is further supported by the consistency in residual whey protein values (0.369–0.332%) in the released whey across the different coagulation temperatures.

In addition, changes in the coagulation temperature of milk proteins significantly influence the moisture content of the resulting protein masses. As shown in Table 3, lowering the coagulation

temperature from 95°C to 65°C results in an increase in the moisture content of the low-fat protein mass by 2.92% and the fatty protein mass by 3.04%.

5.CONCLUSION

The research into the process of thermal acid coagulation of milk proteins has established an optimal mode of preliminary heat treatment of milk (95°C with a holding time of 5 minutes), ensuring the highest degree of utilization of raw material dry substances. This is crucial for promoting waste-free production and protecting the environment.

Scientifically substantiated modes of coagulation for heat-treated milk proteins have been determined: 75°C and 85°C, respectively, for skim and low-fat protein masses. These findings are significant for expanding the range of protein products, including high-quality fresh soft cheeses.

Considering the serious negative environmental consequences of whey discharge and the necessity of greening dairy production, this technology for processing and utilizing whey is highly recommended for widespread implementation in dairy industry enterprises due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness. We express our deep gratitude to the management of the Murodzhonsut International Chemistry Association and the staff of the Service Department of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service for their invaluable assistance in organizing and conducting the experimental work.

6.REFERENCES:

1. Waste-free technology. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waste-free-technology>. Accessed 20 December 2023.
2. Z.U. Karaeva. "Waste-free technologies in the food industry." *News of OshTU*, 2, 184, (2013). http://vestnik.oshtu.kg/images/Journal/20132/prob_estes_i_tehnich_nauk/21_z_u_karaeva1.pdf.
3. N.P. Tarasova, V.A. Zaitsev, V.A. Kuznetsov. "Waste-free, clean and green technologies." *Advances in Chemistry and Chemical Technology*, 4, 19, (2014). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bezothodnye-chistye-i-zelyonye-tehnologii>.
4. E.A. Lebedyantseva, M.N. Ivantsova, I.S. Selezneva. "Whey processing." In *Proceedings of the conference Energy and Resource Saving. Energy Supply. Non-Traditional and Renewable Energy Sources. Nuclear Energy*, Ural Federal University, Yekaterinburg, Russian Federation, December 09–13 (2019), https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/88111/1/eir_2019_113.pdf.
5. G. Khramtsov, P.G. Nesterenko. *Waste-free Technology in the Dairy Industry*. Agropromizdat, Moscow, 1989.
6. G.N. Zhakupova, A.T. Sagandyk, G.A. Nurbekova. "Development of waste-free technology for the production of dairy products." *Bulletin of the Belarusian State Economic University*, 5, 91, (2019). <https://rep.bsatu.by/bitstream/doc/12091/1>.
7. E.F. Kravchenko, O.A. Yakovleva. "Rational use of whey." *Food Industry*, 7, 42, (2007).
8. A.Yu. Prosekov. *Development of Technology for Dairy Products with Aerated Structure Using Plant Raw Materials*. (Author's abstract for the degree of candidate of technical sciences, Kemerovo, 2000).
9. N.N. Maksimyuk, A.N. Denisenko, D.S. Misak. "Biotechnological aspects of processing protein waste of animal origin." *Basic Research*, 9, 44, (2006).
10. Waste-free production. Whey processing capabilities. <https://milberg.ru/novosti/bezotxodnoe-proizvodstvo.-vozmozhnosti-pererabotki-molochnoj-syivorotki>. Accessed 01 September 2021.
11. K.M. Fotykhova. "Development of the dairy industry based on waste-free technologies." In *Proceedings of the conference Scientific Potential of Youth - The Future of Belarus*, Polesie State University, Pinsk, Republic of Belarus, March 31 (2011), 76. <https://rep.polessu.by/handle/123456789>.

12. A.A. Gets. "Directions for diversification of production activities of milk processing enterprises." In *Proceedings of the conference Sustainable Economic Development: State, Problems, Prospects*, Polesie State University, Pinsk, Republic of Belarus, April 23–25 (2009), 1, 14. <https://rep.polessu.by/handle/123456789>.

13. Pavlistova N.A. *Intensification of the Technology of a Multifunctional Protein Product Based on Thermal Acid Coagulation of Secondary Dairy Raw Materials with a High Content of Dry Substances*. (Author's abstract for the degree of candidate of technical sciences, Mogilev, 2018).

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Iskandar Islomov

2024

© When materials are reproduced, the *ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATIO* journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

